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A Recommendation System for Stress Management at the Workplace Using RAG-based LLM

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Abstract. Stress in the workplace is a significant challenge people face in their everyday lives that affects their well-being, and productivity. Large Language Models (LLMs) may function as complementary tools in a wider, work-related, stress management approach, helping occupational mental health professionals handle employees' stressors. Our work explores the use of LLMs in a stress management recommendation system that accepts smartwatch-derived stress indicators and user feedback from scientifically verified questionnaires to provide results. The system employs Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG) to access a curated library of stress management literature, delivering evidence-based recommendations. Our experiments highlight how the input form affects producing grounded results and compare the produced recommendations using different library compositions. While the presented approach may only be used under supervision by mental health experts, it may also help in promptly identifying certain cases that require immediate attention while providing straightforward guidance for milder cases.

Keywords: Stress Management · Recommendation Systems · Retrieval-Augmented Generation · Large Language Models

1 Introduction

Stress has become an inevitable part of our daily lives. Particularly in professional environments, increasing demands, tight deadlines, toxic work environment, role ambiguity, and many other reasons can create a perfect situation for developing chronic stress, decreased productivity, or even physiological and psychological disorders [1]. Healthcare professionals have to endure higher levels of stress than normal people, due to the nature of their occupation, but in some cases also because of budget cuts which strain them even more [2]. Research has indicated that workplace stress is associated with the presence of cardiovascular disease, type 2 diabetes, and depression symptoms [3]; thus, addressing it constitutes an important objective, both for individuals who suffer from it, but also for the organization that employs them.

Organizations can be proactive in managing uncertainty and dynamic conditions that operate as stressors, by improving working conditions through the use of Artificial Intelligence (AI) to share work between humans and AI. The concept of Sliding Work Sharing (SWS) where activities can dynamically shift between human and AI, based on situational context, machine confidence levels, and human interactions, offers a promising approach, especially in the healthcare sector [4]. AI systems can lead to improved diagnostic accuracy and reduced number of errors in the field of healthcare, while empowering patients to monitor their health through specially tailored applications [5]. Of course, the human factor is of paramount importance since most AI applications are still at an early-stage, with limited real-world validation which in turn necessitates rigorous clinical testing and oversight. Research suggests that human-AI hybrid teams can outperform either humans or AI alone, through humans being smart about when to trust AI recommendations during decision-making [6]. Accordingly regarding mental health, occupational doctors have the opportunity to enhance the results of their effort with the use of tools and technologies that utilize AI [7]. A clear, measurement-based view of staff's physical and mental well-being can be provided by remote monitoring systems that analyze stress indicators and suggest targeted interventions, subject to approval by the occupational doctors, to help mitigate staff burnout or stress and improve working conditions [6].

Existing studies in the field of mental health, regarding question answering [8,9,10,11], assisting in diagnosing medical conditions [12,13], or providing AI-based therapy sessions [14] or recommendations, have been noted. Regarding the latter, there has been an ongoing effort to develop methods that focus on providing recommendations. This part of the research area is critical since a *Large Language Model (LLM)* can be trained in problem-specific datasets, but there is still the issue of hallucinations. In this case, the LLM output may lack a logical foundation [15] or be biased [16]. To face this challenge, an approach that has been proposed is *Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG)*, in which the LLM gains access to sources of information relevant to the problem at hand, allowing the output text to be based on actual sources. RAG-based recommendation systems have been proposed for a few areas like medical treatment [17] and clinical protocol selection [18], and in the case of mental health, recommendations for patients that suffer from dementia [19]. It is obvious that stress, albeit a very important factor that affects multiple aspects of our daily lives, is yet to receive the amount of attention it deserves. Its management necessitates further research towards the use of LLM-based methods for its solution, assisting individuals to manage their stress, especially occupational which costs valuable resources, as already mentioned. However, the successful collaboration between humans and AI in human-centric domains, like healthcare, faces certain challenges. While AI holds immense promise for enhancing efficiency and accuracy, its adoption is heavily influenced by trust, transparency, and effective collaboration frameworks [20, 21, 22].

This raises the research questions of a) how an AI system can assist occupational doctors in helping hospital employees manage their stressors, b) how this human-AI collaboration can be built on trust to ensure reliable outcomes and, c) how employees can provide the necessary feedback to receive personalized assistance in managing their

stress. Inspired by this, the work presented in this paper introduces a recommendation system that employs an LLM in combination with RAG to access a library that contains stress management-related textbooks and provide grounded recommendations aimed at medical staff to help them manage their workplace-related stress. The recommendations are to be subject to approval from occupational doctors whose decision-making is augmented by the recommendation system. We utilize *GPT-4o* from *OpenAI* for this purpose and compare its recommendation capabilities against the recently released *DeepSeek-R1* [23] LLM. The input for our approach comprises an indicator that denotes the user’s stress, and data obtained through the clinically validated *Depression Anxiety Stress Scales-21 (DASS-21)* [24] questionnaire. The stress indicator may be provided directly from wearable devices, like smartwatches built-in functions, or through more sophisticated methods that take into account multiple biomarkers, like Heart Rate (HR), Heart Rate Variability (HRV), and others [25], to yield the same result. In our case, we simulate the stress indicator values using the *Huawei Watch 3* smartwatch as a reference, generating additional values per dataset sample to account for all possible stress categories. We conduct experiments regarding the practicality in using numerical values, like scores and stress indicator values, in the LLM input prompt, given the problem context. We also evaluate the similarity in the recommendations using different book combinations in the RAG library and extract useful insights from the produced recommendations.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. In Section 2, the relevant literature is reviewed. Section 3 contains the specifics of the implemented approach and the composition of the stress management library, while Section 4 presents the conducted experiments and their results. Section 5 discusses the concerns and limitations of the presented method. The paper concludes with the future research steps.

2 Related Work

Over the past years, several healthcare-oriented approaches that explore the capabilities of chatbots in helping diagnose an illness or providing information through questions have been developed. *Kazi et al.* [26] implemented an early approach using AI Markup Language (AIML) to convert user input to SQL queries and generate natural language responses from a medical knowledge source, the *Unified Medical Language System (UMLS)*, with varying levels of expert acceptance depending on query type. *Katariya et al.* [27] described a conversational healthcare chatbot designed to evaluate symptoms and provide disease information based on online sources. *Prayitno et al.* [28] created a chatbot that diagnoses illnesses, should the user not know their condition, and suggests an appropriate treatment. The method used cosine similarity and ID3 decision trees to identify the disease that caused the symptoms, and of course, the suggestions came with a disclaimer.

The introduction of Transformers in 2017 changed the scene [29], allowing the development of LLMs. In general, LLMs follow a transformer-based architecture and are trained using massive datasets that contain general textual information. Among the first LLMs was *BERT* [30], a bidirectional encoder-only transformer model that saw a period of wide usage before the release of the first *GPT* model, which was a decoder-

only generative transformer. Other well-known LLMs were released in the following years, improving on the existing ones, with *GPT-3.5*, *GPT-4* and *LLaMA2* being among the most popular [31, 32].

Recommendation systems are a particularly interesting field for LLM research. Yang et al. [15] developed a framework for personalized nutrition-oriented food recommendations. The input is retrieved and filtered before it is used to form the prompt that is going to be used in the LLM (*GPT-3.5-turbo*). The input contains the user's query, personal data, and population data to gain a broader perspective for the recommendation. It is acknowledged, though, that the LLM may occasionally produce information that may lead to nonsensical recommendations, despite being able to comprehend the user's input. Another example is a solution that combines 3D human pose estimation and an LLM that generates exercise recommendations, developed by *Dibenedetto et al.* [16]. The suggestions are based on the detected posture issues, and the evaluation of the method was performed by 2 physiotherapists who provided feedback on 10 different scenarios. *Argymbay et al.* [33] utilized *BioMistral-7B* for personalized health advice and answering stroke-related questions. Recommendations that were retrieved from the Internet could be provided while the authors evaluated their work on several medical datasets and acquired feedback from expert clinicians, noting potential inaccuracies with wearable technology measurements. Pairing recommendations are also a use case scenario for LLMs with *Berger et al.* [34] developing a recommender system for matching patients with similar rare diseases, evaluating various approaches, including LLM-based user profile summarization, while *Ruan et al.* [18] created a clinical trial protocol recommender using Neo4j graph databases and *GPT-4* to extract information based on user input and eligibility criteria, though they noted limitations in considering entity distances within the utilized knowledge graph.

In the field of mental healthcare, several works have explored LLM applications, like *Farhat et al.* [35], who assessed ChatGPT's effectiveness in providing mental health support for anxiety and depression, concluding it may serve as a complementary resource, supporting medical professionals, but is not suitable for prescription recommendations. *DoctorGLM* [9], a Chinese dialogue LLM, was created for mental disorder classification and question answering purposes. It had the additional advantage of being a budget-friendly LLM to develop because of the notable idea of using ChatGPT to generate a small dataset of English-to-Chinese translated medical reports. The dataset was then used to fine-tune a *BART*-based model that handled the translation and production of a much larger dataset that was used to train *DoctorGLM*. *ChatGLM-6b* [36] formed the basis for the whole implementation, having been optimized for Chinese question-answering and dialogue. *Yu et al.* [14] refined *DialoGPT* using transcribed data from real-world therapy sessions. The refined model's output is then used as context along with the initial user input, forming a combined input for the ChatGPT-3.5 API to produce the final output. In that case, while the user feedback graded the chatbot favorably, it was also noted that several improvements could be made to achieve a degree of more personalized advice, but also to better handle users who have provided input that relates to harming themselves.

The research on LLMs brought to the surface the problem of hallucinations, which caused the model to produce unbased answers. Another important issue was the generation of biased responses. These challenges led some researchers to pivot towards RAG, which enabled the LLMs to ground their reasoning on relevant documents from trustworthy sources of information [37]. Especially in healthcare, providing answers based on concrete sources is of paramount importance.

Several studies have investigated the application of RAG in healthcare contexts. *Raja et al.* [11] developed a medical chatbot that leverages RAG to retrieve information from a source library through a knowledge graph, generating responses that are subsequently transformed to voice output. *Zakka et al.* [17] proposed a system that uses external tools (search engines and medical databases) to answer clinical queries and provide treatment information with in-text citations for improved safety. Their evaluation with board-certified clinicians showed superior accuracy compared to ChatGPT. *Xiong et al.* [38] presented *MedRAG*, a systematic toolkit for RAG that leverages various corpora (biomedical, clinical, and general medicine) and introduced *MIRAGE*, a benchmark including 7,663 questions from five medical QA datasets. Similarly, *Lozano et al.* [39] created a system comprising four cooperating LLMs (GPT-3.5 and GPT-4), alongside information retrievers that access PubMed and Semantic Scholar and filter relevant sources using an LLM binary classifier, which are summarized for the final response. *Yu et al.* [12] developed a zero-shot retrieval augmented method using LLaMA2 and GPT-3.5 to diagnose cardiac diseases and sleep apnoea from electrocardiogram data, noting potential limitations in capturing signal nuances that may cause misdiagnosis.

Regarding mental health, *Sree et al.* [10] developed *MEDGPT*, a RAG-based chatbot that retrieves information from external sources like PDFs, CSV files, and PubMed documents to answer healthcare queries and perform diagnoses for physical and mental health. *Cremschi et al.* [13] developed *LLMind Chat*, which utilizes *Google Gemma 2 (27B)* and RAG to assist psychologists with diagnostic decision making according to the *International Classification of Diseases - 11th rev. (ICD 11)* and the *Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders*, achieving remarkable accuracy but still requiring human supervision, especially for cases with overlapping mental disorders. *Hu et al.* [19] developed a RAG-based LLM, following GPT-4 architecture, that uses anonymized patient records and cognitive assessment results to generate tailored care recommendations for patients with mild to moderate degrees of dementia. Finally, *Lai et al.* [8] developed *Psy-LLM*, which combines pre-trained LLMs with professional Q&A from psychologists and psychological articles in a RAG framework to provide mental health advice. The *PanGu* model, developed by Huawei's Pengcheng Laboratory, and the *WenZhong* model, developed by the Idea Research Institute, served as the basis for this method. The data used in this work originates from a substantial number of Chinese psychological publications from public websites.

To our knowledge, limited research has explored the generation of stress management recommendations through AI-human collaboration, particularly involving occupational doctors—a gap this study seeks to address. This is especially relevant in the context of integrating user inputs, such as biomarker data collected from wearable devices, and self-reported psychological assessments. The approach presented in this

paper utilizes the *GPT-4o* which is versatile and robust in handling text and is the current flagship model of OpenAI. Using this, we produce recommendations and compare them against the output from a *DeepSeek-R1* [23] LLM which, while being a relatively compact open-source model, still maintains strong performance but also, reasoning capabilities which is an important asset for a recommendation system. To provide the LLM with additional context to better understand the sources of stress, we also employ the shortened version of the *Depression, Anxiety, Stress Scales (DASS)* questionnaire developed by *Lovibond & Lovibond* [24]. The original DASS assessment comprises 42 questions and was designed to measure the negative emotional states of depression, anxiety, and stress. The questionnaire is meant to be used as a self-assessment test, with each question corresponding to one of the three negative emotions. Each answer produces a score, and the total per emotional state assigns the person to one of the five levels of severity (“Normal”, “Mild”, “Moderate”, “Severe”, and “Extremely Severe”). RAG is also employed in our approach, with the composition of the used textbook library being discussed later on.

3 Methodology

This study presents a RAG-based approach for generating personalized stress management recommendations for healthcare staff using an LLM. The approach is designed to act as an AI advisor for the occupational doctors, who work with the system to produce final recommendations. While the use of RAG helps ensure that the generated recommendations are grounded in reliable sources of knowledge, occupational doctors must review each AI-generated recommendation before it is delivered to clinical staff, ensuring safe and trustworthy AI integration. The system accepts input from the user in the form of *DASS-21*¹ psychological self-assessment which is chosen due to the scientific background that governs it, but also due to the availability of public data through the *Depression Anxiety Stress Scales Responses*² dataset which is described later and provides real user feedback for our experiments.

A stress indicator (index) that denotes the user’s stress, based on biomarker data, is also included as input for our method. In general, the stress indicator is either provided from wearable devices (e.g., Huawei smartwatch, Apple Watch, etc.) through their built-in stress measuring functionality or an offline procedure that collects biomarker data (i.e., HR, HRV, etc.) across time and calculates the indicator.

The overall objective of the method is to provide evidence-based recommendations grounded in established stress management literature, given the feedback from the user’s answers in the questionnaire and the stress they experience during their day. The grounded nature of the recommendations helps improve the reliability of the approach as an AI advisor in the context of human-AI collaboration and may increase the human trust in such systems. Our implementation utilizes GPT-4o, a variant of GPT-4 LLM

¹ <https://maic.qld.gov.au/wp-content/uploads/2016/07/DASS-21.pdf>. Last accessed on 29 May 2025.

² <https://www.kaggle.com/datasets/lucasgreenwell/depression-anxiety-stress-scales-responses/data>. Last accessed on 29 May 2025.

developed by OpenAI and provided by *Microsoft Azure*. For comparison, we also produce results using a distilled version of the DeepSeek-R1 LLM. The latter is provided through the *Groq Cloud*, and the distilled version of the model is fine-tuned from the *Llama-3.3-70B-Instruct* base model while retaining the reasoning patterns of DeepSeek-R1.

3.1 DASS-21 Questionnaire Responses and Stress Indicator

Answered samples of the *DASS-21* questionnaire are acquired from the *Depression Anxiety Stress Scales Responses* dataset which is available on *Kaggle*. The data that comprise it were collected from 2017 to 2019 through a survey hosted on a non-profit website whose objectives were the education of the public about psychology and the collection of data for psychological research. The survey included the DASS questionnaire and several additional questions about the volunteers. The dataset has a size of 39775 samples and contains only the answers of those volunteers who have explicitly stated the accuracy in their given answers and have granted permission to have them used for research purposes.

As was mentioned earlier, each question pertains to one of the three negative emotional states. The total score for each state is calculated per answered questionnaire, and the samples were grouped into categories regarding the combinations of the different severity levels of the emotional states. The score values of the emotional states range from 0 to 42, and the meaning of the score is interpreted according to the description of the DASS questionnaire. A sample from each of the 18 most represented combinations of severity levels were selected for the experiments (see Table 1). The most represented combinations account for the 35.4% or 14078 samples of the dataset. It must be noted that samples that had either of the three emotional states classified as *Extremely Severe* were excluded. This was decided because it became apparent that conditions that fall in the spectrum of *Severe* or *Extremely Severe* negative emotional states, have an increased chance of being affected by a multitude of reasons. Except for that, another reason was that, during the early experimentation stage, it was noted that the recommendation system, given sets of answers that scored at least one emotional state into the “*Severe*” level, and the option to refer the user to a mental health expert, it recommended in most cases that the user visits an expert.

Since the *Depression Anxiety Stress Scales Responses* dataset does not contain any data from smartwatch devices regarding biometric stress, a stress indicator (index) value was used per questionnaire in our experiments. The values assigned per questionnaire result are based on the Huawei Watch 3 built-in stress measurement functionality. The measured stress is an integer value from 1 to 99. The individual is considered to be in a *Relaxed* state regarding their stress, when the measurement is within 1 and 29. The stress is considered to be *Low* when the value is the range 30 to 59, *Medium* if the value is from 60 to 79, and *High* should the value be above 79 and up to 99. For each sample questionnaire, we generate 4 samples, each one having assigned the median value per stress category. The assigned values for the stress index are 15, 45, 70 and 90. Thus, a total number of 72 questionnaire samples result from this process and are used to produce the recommendations.

Table 1. The 18 samples from the Depression Anxiety Stress Scales Responses dataset. Survey ID refers to the assigned ID from the dataset. Depression-Anxiety-Stress scores result from the given answers per questionnaire, according to the DASS-21 score calculation method.

ID	Survey ID	Depression Score	Anxiety Score	Stress Score
1	26289	8	4	8
2	1203	0	8	2
3	22929	0	10	12
4	22037	4	18	6
5	10053	12	6	6
6	36641	10	10	10
7	7119	16	2	12
8	17473	14	8	12
9	9097	14	12	14
10	9550	18	12	18
11	7692	16	14	20
12	28706	14	18	10
13	6414	14	18	16
14	9241	20	18	20
15	10079	26	2	12
16	13430	22	14	2
17	2600	22	10	22
18	8409	22	18	22

3.2 Retrieval-Augmented Generation

The RAG approach is employed to ensure evidence-based recommendations. The source textbooks that RAG makes use of are loaded and split into text chunks of 1024 tokens and an overlap of 512 tokens. The whole body of text is used to generate the vector database. Each LLM uses a different embedding method. For GPT-4o the *Text-Embedding-3-Large* model provided by OpenAI is used to provide text embeddings with up to 3072 dimensions. In the case of DeepSeek-R1, the *HuggingFace* embeddings, available through the *LangChain* framework are utilized. For the embedding generation process, the *All-Mpnet-BaseV2* sentence-transformer is utilized. The model maps each chunk of text to a 768-dimensional vector space. In either case, the generated embedding resulting from the input prompt that contains feedback from the user is then used as input for the information retriever that performs a similarity search in the vector database. The search result is a list of the 10 most relevant to the input embedding, pieces of text, which are then used as context in the LLM input.

Regarding the source literature, it comprises textbooks, which are presented in Table 2. The selected bibliography on stress management emerged after thorough research on the Internet. The search was conducted through Google and Google Scholar using keywords like “*stress management books*”, “*books for managing stress*”, and “*stress management books for healthcare professionals*” and choosing results from 2000 onwards. *ChatGPT* provided by OpenAI and *Claude* provided by Anthropic were also used in the search. The search is not exhaustive because its purpose is to include a decent number of sources that are accessible online and can be comprehended by the regular reader. Therefore, results that required some sort of payment for access were not included. The books are not assessed for their quality by any mental health expert; however, the main criterion in selecting the books was the scientific background and current job occupation of the authors, as well as any scientific managers who participated in the editing of the text. The authors are either professionals in the medical field, such as doctors or psychologists, or professors of medicine or a related subject, at respectable university institutions, such as Harvard, Stanford, and the University of Massachusetts, with many of them having active participation in the field of research. A characteristic of the bibliography is that there is a significant reference to mind-body medicine and the intersection of medical practice with stress reduction, mindfulness, and holistic approaches to health and wellness.

Table 2. The literature about stress management recommendations that was used as a source for RAG.

ID	Title	Author(s)	Year	Publisher
#1	Stress Management, Approaches for Preventing and Reducing Stress [40]	Casey, Aggie	2013	Harvard Health Publications
#2	The Relaxation Response [41]	Benson, Herbert	2000	William Morrow Paperbacks
#3	The Stress Proof Brain [42]	Greenberg, Melanie	2017	New Harbinger Publications
#4	Full Catastrophe Living [43]	Kabat-Zinn, Jon	2013	Random House
#5	The stress management handbook: A practical guide to staying calm, keeping cool, and avoiding blow-ups [44]	Selhub, Eva	2019	Skyhorse Publishing
#6	Why Zebras Don't Get Ulcers, An Updated Guide to Stress, Stress Related Diseases, and Coping [45]	Sapolsky, Robert M	1998	Barnes & Noble Books
#7	Management for Primary Healthcare Professionals [46]	Rout, Usha R. and Rout, Jaya K.	2002	Springer

3.3 Prompt Engineering

The presented approach uses two prompt templates which are depicted in Figures 1 and 2. Both convey the same meaning to the LLM, requesting a set of recommendations aimed for healthcare professionals and stating the same rules and restrictions are the end. Their difference lies in the way the user feedback, emotional state scores and the smartwatch stress index are communicated.

In the first template, depicted in Figure 1, the actual numerical values for the stress index and the DASS-21 scores for the negative emotional states are embedded in the template along with instructions about the range of their possible values. The actual DASS-21 questions with the numerical score answers as filled by the user are also embedded in the prompt with the meaning of each assigned score per question. In the second template, depicted in Figure 2, the stress index and DASS-21 scores are substituted by categorical values, words that correspond to the respective category per value. Thus, the stress index value is substituted by the stress categories from the Huawei Watch 3 (*Relaxed, Low, Medium and High*) and the DASS scores are replaced by the severity levels defined (*Normal, Mild, Moderate and Severe*). The answered questionnaire is also summarized, using the GPT-4o model, into a cohesive paragraph that is then embedded in the prompt.

Both templates conclude with some instructions regarding the case where the user seems capable of self-managing their stress and the case where the user is deemed by the LLM to need professional mental health support. In any other case, the LLM is asked to provide three one-sentence, concise recommendations. An important part of the templates is the last statement which restricts the LLM from making recommendations that are not based on the provided RAG sources.

The reason for using those two templates is to examine the ability of the context retriever to fetch relevant information from the vector database.

I am a healthcare professional. You are specialized in giving stress management recommendations that target healthcare professionals. To make a recommendation, take into account the following context:

- My stress index as indicated by heart rate measurements and ranges from 0 (relaxed) to 99 (high). My stress index is {stress_idx}.
- My depression level which results from a psychological assessment and ranges from 0(minimum value) to 42(maximum value). My depression level is {depression_score}.
- My anxiety level which results from a psychological assessment and ranges from 0(minimum value) to 42(maximum value). My anxiety level is {anxiety_score}.
- My stress level which results from a psychological assessment and ranges from 0(minimum value) to 42(maximum value). My stress level is {stress_score}.
- My scores to a survey. I scored each statement of the survey to denote how much does the statement applies to my situation. The meaning of the score values is:
 - 0 (did not apply to me)
 - 1 (applied to me to some degree, or some of the time.)
 - 2 (applied to me to a considerable degree or a good part of time)
 - 3 (applies to me very much or most of the time)

The statements and their scores are: "{dass21}"

Give me three recommendations for managing my stress. Use one sentence maximum for each recommendation and keep it as concise as possible. If you think that I am OK regarding my stress, you can say it. If you think that I should seek professional mental health support, do not recommend anything else. If you don't know what recommendation to make, just say that you don't know, don't try to make up an answer. Strictly only rely on the sources provided in generating your response. Never rely on external sources.

Fig. 1. The prompt template used for numerical value input. {stress_idx}, {depression_score}, {anxiety_score}, and {stress_score} correspond to stress index, depression, anxiety and stress scores, respectively. {dass21} corresponds to the questions-answers input from the questionnaire. All values in brackets are replaced on runtime.

I am a healthcare professional. You are specialized in giving stress management recommendations that target healthcare professionals. To make the recommendations, take into account the following context:

- My {stress_idx_category} level of stress as indicated by heart rate measurements.
- My {depression_lvl} level of depression which results from a psychological assessment.
- My {anxiety_lvl} level of anxiety which results from a psychological assessment.
- My {stress_lvl} level of stress which results from a psychological assessment.
- My psychological assessment summary is: "{dass21_summary}"

Give me three recommendations for managing my stress.

Use one sentence maximum for each recommendation and keep it as concise as possible. If you think that I am OK regarding my stress, you can say it. If you think that I should seek professional mental health support, do not recommend anything else. If you don't know what recommendation to make, just say that you don't know, don't try to make up an answer. Strictly only rely on the sources provided in generating your response. Never rely on external sources.

Fig. 2. The prompt template used for categorical input values. {stress_idx_category}, {depression_lvl}, {anxiety_lvl}, and {stress_lvl} correspond to stress index category from Huawei Watch 3, depression, anxiety and stress severity levels, respectively. {dass21_summary} corresponds to the questionnaire produced summary. All values in brackets are replaced on runtime.

Table 3. The recommendations as recorded by the human annotators. The Description contains a summary of the recommendation, and the Frequency relates to the frequency of occurrence per recommendation.

Label	Description	Frequency
1	Practice mindfulness or meditation	234
2	Practice relaxation techniques, like deep breathing or progressive muscle relaxation	262
3	Use visualization techniques to focus on positive outcomes	55
4	Silently repeating a calming phrase, to shift focus and reduce nervous energy	72
5	Use cognitive restructuring to reframe negative thoughts	158
6	Set aside time for activities, hobbies to enhance well-being	162
7	Get regular physical activity	443
8	Engage in self-care activities, ensure adequate sleep and nutrition	158
9	Keep a journal to trace negative emotions	69
10	Spend time / connect with friends/family	218
11	Spend time / connect with colleagues	217
12	Take regular short breaks from work	55
13	Set small achievable goals	32
14	Set clear work-life boundaries to manage workload	32
15	Prioritize tasks and set realistic goals	79
16	Implement time management techniques	29
17	Consider participating in a stress management course	31
18	Listen attentively and express appreciation to others	32
19	Use assertiveness skills to communicate effectively	14
20	Consider talking to a mental health professional	5
21	Seek professional mental health support	196

4 Experiments

This section contains the evaluation metrics that were used, the description of each experiment, and the produced results. We conduct 2 experiments: a) a comparison between GPT-4o and DeepSeek-R1 in their capability to produce recommendations, using the 2 different prompt templates we mentioned previously, and b) using the best model combination of LLM model and prompt template, a comparison of the ranked lists of recommendations produced using different RAG library compositions.

4.1 Evaluation Metrics

To compare GPT-4o and DeepSeek-R1 we use evaluation metrics provided by the RAGAs [47] which is an evaluation framework for RAG-based methods. In specific, we use the *Context Precision* which measures the proportion of relevant retrieved contexts to the total number of retrieved contexts and its value ranges from 0 to 1.

$$\text{Context Precision@}K = \frac{\sum_{k=1}^K (\text{Precision@}k \times v_k)}{\text{Total number of relevant items in the top } K \text{ results}}$$

$$\text{Precision@}k = \frac{\text{true positives@}k}{(\text{true positive@}k + \text{false positives@}k)}$$

Where K is the total number of retrieved contexts and $v_k \in \{0, 1\}$ is the relevance indicator at rank k . Another evaluation metric used is the *Faithfulness* which measures how consistent is the method output to the retrieved contexts. It ranges from 0 to 1 with higher scores indicating better consistency. The final metric used for the evaluation is the *Answer Relevancy* which measures how relevant is the output to the user input.

$$\text{Answer Relevancy} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \text{cosine similarity}(E_{g_i}, E_o)$$

where E_{g_i} is the embedding of the user input and E_o is the embedding of the method output. N refers to the number of asked questions and in the current context is equal to 1 since there is only one request for recommendations.

Regarding the second part of the experiments, to evaluate the similarity between ranked recommendation lists, we employed *Rank Biased Overlap (RBO)* as proposed by *Webber et al.* [48]. RBO is an intersection-based metric and was selected for its advantages over traditional correlation metrics such as Kendall’s Tau, as it specifically addresses situations where we have to compare lists of different lengths or attention has to be paid to elements located higher in the list. Especially the latter is an important reason to select this evaluation approach since the presented method is a recommendation system. A publicly available implementation of the RBO metric is used for the evaluation, as was defined in Eq. 23 of the relevant paper. Parameter p defines the amount of weight to be given to the higher ranks of the list and is set to 0.8 . Parameter d defines the depth of list elements at which the weights are dispersed and is set to 10 . The extrapolation option for the implementation was set to True. RBO values range from 0 (no overlap) to 1 (identical rankings).

4.2 Experiments Description

In the first experiment we compare GPT-4o and DeepSeek-R1 in their capability to produce recommendations. The objective is to determine the impact of using numerical values in the prompt input of the model. The survey samples presented in Table 1 using different combinations of stress indicator values, as described in Section 3.1, were used

as input for the LLM models for a total of 72 samples. The two prompt templates presented in Figures 1 and 2 were used to form the input. For the first template, the actual numerical values for the Depression, Anxiety and Stress scores, and the Stress Index were embedded in the prompt template, along with the actual questions and scored responses per questions of the DASS-21 questionnaire. In the case of the second template, the numerical values were first substituted to their respective categorical values, as defined in the DASS questionnaire developed by *Lovibond & Lovibond* [24]. The questionnaire was summarized using GPT-4o in a concise paragraph that was also embedded in the prompt input.

Regarding the second experiment, as mentioned earlier, based on the results from the first experiment, the GPT-4o is employed using the categorical values setup of the second prompt template. The system produces 3 one-sentence recommendations, however, with the produced recommendations being not deterministic, since the temperature parameter for the LLM is set to 0. Therefore, a combination of the same 3 recommendations is not repeated when we run the method numerous times in a row. Some recommendations, given the context, have a higher frequency of occurrence than others. We capture this frequency in our experiments as “*weight*”.

Eight library compositions were selected for this experiment. The first among them includes all the available books in the library, while the remaining 7 library compositions contain only a single book each, from the books presented in Table 2. The objective in this experiment is to examine the similarity of the recommendations produced by the whole library and each individual book alone, resulting in 7 test scenarios of comparison in total.

For each questionnaire from the 72 questionnaire samples used to produce the recommendations, we executed the method 3 times with the same input. The number of occurrences per recommendation was recorded. A recommendation that occurred in all 3 iterations received *weight*=3, a recommendation that occurred in only 2 out of 3 iterations received *weight*=2, and so on. Two recommendations from different method executions are considered the same when they have the same semantic meaning. This meaning was determined by human annotators who reviewed all the recommendations produced during the experiments. Every answered questionnaire is accompanied by several recommendations, each of which has a different weight, thus rendering the recommendations list, in essence, a ranked list. Table 3 contains a list of concise recommendations as they were recorded by the annotators and the frequency of their appearance during the experiments. The annotators had the task to review all the recommendations, extract the actual recommendations after each method run and group them according to their meaning. This process was important for the more accurate comparison of the method results using different library compositions since the recommendations have been reviewed for their meaningfulness by humans and validated by experts in the mental health field.

4.3 Results

The results from the GPT-4o – DeepSeek-R1 comparison are presented in Table 4. The table highlights the importance of using words to describe the numerical values

that are used as input for the method, in order to achieve better Context Precision which is essential in retrieving relevant context from the RAG library. Regardless of the LLM model and the used prompt template, Answer Relevancy is more or less the same since in every case, the user input produces a number of recommendations as output.

Table 4. Comparison of recommendation results using GPT-4o and DeepSeek-R1 models, using two different prompt templates to formalize the numerical score-index values. Cont. Pr., Faith., and Ans. Rel. correspond to Context Precision, Faithfulness and Answer Relevancy evaluation metrics, respectively. Metric results are grouped by the type of input form, which is either numerical, or categorical.

Model	Numerical			Categorical		
	Cont. Pr.	Faith.	Ans. Rel.	Cont. Pr.	Faith	Ans. Rel.
GPT-4o	0.001	0.8333	0.5033	0.2124	0.6173	0.4598
DeepSeek-R1	0.0	0.4502	0.4997	0.013	0.7381	0.4688

The results from the second experiment are visualized in Table 5 and indicate how much impact each book alone has on the recommendations produced from the whole library. The books with the greatest impact are the books #1 and #6 which contain more general stress management techniques, compared to book #7 which comes in third place and contains recommendations that are healthcare-oriented, given its content. Figure 3 presents the five most popular recommendations per library composition, with recommendations like practicing meditation-mindfulness being more popular with some books while the recommendation about engaging in regular physical activity being popular in general. The figure highlights the fact that some books are more oriented towards certain recommendations, thus including them in the library provides the system with a more rounded perspective of the available stress management techniques.

Table 5. The similarity of the ranked recommendations produced by each individual book and the whole library.

ID	Test Scenario	RBO
1	All books – Book #1 only	0.8395
2	All books – Book #2 only	0.2162
3	All books – Book #3 only	0.2367
4	All books – Book #4 only	0.3076
5	All books – Book #5 only	0.3505
6	All books – Book #6 only	0.4651
7	All books – Book #7 only	0.3793

Fig. 3. Top 5 recommendations by frequency of occurrence, per library composition. Each recommendation is denoted by its ID as presented in Table 3.

5 Discussion

The results from the first experiment clearly show that using numerical values does not improve the search for relevant results in library sources. The problem formulation and structure contained in the input prompt are essential when using LLMs to solve problems. However, converting numerical values into verbal descriptions alone helps in the search for sources in books. This is because, as shown by the results, emotional states such as depression, anxiety, and stress are difficult to quantify. Additionally, the existing quantification through the DASS-21 questionnaire is not connected to stress management method proposals, as evidenced by our search of public literature for stress management manuals, described in Section 3.

The value of the Context Precision metric remains low, indicating two necessary improvements. First, the connection between quantified emotional states and stress management techniques needs further research. Second, collecting data that establishes this connection is useful to better consolidate the recommendations in valid sources. The latter can be achieved with the contribution of the human factor and few-shot learning techniques. It is important to note that a low score in Context Precision does not necessarily mean that the recommendation is wrong in itself, but rather that it relied less on user input, making the recommendation more general.

The score in the Faithfulness metric indicates how well recommendations remain grounded in the retrieved context from the RAG library. Both LLMs achieve values of at least 0.6, with DeepSeek-R1 clearly having an advantage in relating its recommendations to the retrieved contexts.

An important consideration is that the stress management recommendation system presented in this paper, like any similar AI system that provides advice, is designed to work jointly with the occupational doctors as an assistant. The overall goal is synergy, combining functions machines do best with those best suited for clinicians. The AI should focus on low-level, non-critical tasks to free up clinicians for patient

examination and diagnosis, rather than solely automating the recommendation task, attempting to replace doctors or dictate their actions [5], [20].

The questionnaires used to generate the recommendations have escalating degrees of criticality, based on the Depression, Anxiety, and Stress scores. For situations that are not serious based on those values, the system may provide advice with minimal supervision. However, higher scores may indicate situations too complex for the system to provide reliable advice. Human intuition and experience give doctors the advantage of perceiving subtle cues that AI cannot capture [22]. These increased values essentially signal critical situations where inaccurate recommendations must be eliminated for the person's benefit. In such cases, the doctor overrides or improves the inaccurate AI-generated recommendation which may be based on insufficient RAG sources or biased due to imbalanced training datasets. Cultural and social context play an essential role in providing stress management advice, which can only be adapted to the user by the doctor.

Among the improvements that could advance human-AI collaboration, human feedback is a potentially useful way to improve the system by having modified recommendation lists stored in a library for future reference. However, focus should also be placed in improving transparency and explainability of the system's rationale in decision-making. Medical professionals desire upfront information about the properties, known strengths and limitations of the AI [21]. This ensures that healthcare professionals' attitudes towards AI are positive while also fostering a sense of trust. The initial introduction to an AI assistant is also very important to that end, since it provides a general view of the way the assistant functions in a way relatable to day-to-day practices. This involves grounding performance metrics in human-relatable benchmarks, thus evaluating AI performance on known human errors and edge cases.

6 Conclusion

This paper presented an AI recommender system that receives input data from smartwatch sensors and questionnaire feedback from users, and collaborates with occupational doctors to provide stress management recommendations to healthcare staff. Systems that gather personal data must comply with GDPR regulations, to protect sensitive information by implementing layers of user pseudonymization, as well as security best practices against data breaches. Another critical concern relates to the data incompleteness of RAG-based recommendation systems, where careful selection of valid, peer-reviewed library sources is crucial. Including sources that mitigate cultural bias helps make better informed recommendations. Increasing the variance of cases and relevant advice provided in the sources, also helps equalize the representation of instances, leading to a more holistic view. Transparency and explainability help provide insights into how the LLM utilizes the provided sources. An equally important ethical consideration relates to the risk of over-reliance on AI systems and the potential reduction of clinicians' skills. A recommendation system like the one presented in this paper would face serious limitations in fields – unlike in healthcare, where its outputs are not subject to expert validation. This is an important consideration when contemplating its expansion into other domains that provide advice or

recommendations without human involvement, as such use poses significant risks to users and increases the likelihood of faulty results.

The next steps of our research may include the evaluation of the generated lists of recommendations by mental health professionals and the collection of relevant data for further research. This may serve to train problem-specific LLMs in making recommendations without the use of the RAG mechanism or use the collected data as an additional source for the RAG library. The literature used by the RAG has to also be reviewed to improve its quality. Another important aspect for improvement is the introduction of a stress indicator, instead of relying on the stress index measurements of commercially available smartwatches. This will provide useful feedback from the user's biomarker readings, along with the inclusion of additional biomarkers, like Heart Rate Variability (HRV).

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References

1. T. W. Colligan and E. M. Higgins, "Workplace stress: Etiology and consequences," *J. Workplace Behav. Health*, vol. 21, pp. 89–97, July 2006.
2. J. Wells, "The impact of stress amongst health professionals," *J. Ment. Health*, vol. 20, pp. 111–114, Apr. 2011.
3. D. C. Ganster and C. C. Rosen, "Work stress and employee health: A multidisciplinary review," *J. Manage.*, vol. 39, pp. 1085–1122, July 2013.
4. I. Maglogiannis, F. Trastelis, M. Kalogeropoulos, A. Khan, P. Gallos, A. Menychtas, C. Panagopoulos, P. Papachristou, N. Islam, A. Wolff, "AI4Work Project: Human-Centric Digital Twin Approaches to Trustworthy AI and Robotics for Improved Working Conditions in Healthcare and Education Sectors". *Stud. Health Technol. Inform.*, vol. 316, pp. 1013–1017, Aug. 2024.
5. E. J. Topol, "High-performance medicine: the convergence of human and artificial intelligence," *Nat. Med.*, vol. 25, pp. 44–56, Jan. 2019.
6. C. Reverberi, T. Rigon, A. Solari, C. Hassan, P. Cherubini, GI Genius CADx Study Group, and A. Cherubini, "Experimental evidence of effective human-AI collaboration in medical decision-making," *Sci. Rep.*, vol. 12, p. 14952, Sept. 2022.
7. A. Pavlopoulos, T. Rachiotis, and I. Maglogiannis, "An overview of tools and technologies for anxiety and depression management using AI," *Appl. Sci. (Basel)*, vol. 14, no. 19, p. 9068, Oct. 2024.
8. T. Lai, Y. Shi, Z. Du, J. Wu, K. Fu, Y. Dou, and Z. Wang, "Supporting the demand on mental health services with AI-based conversational large language models (LLMs)," *BioMedInformatics*, vol. 4, pp. 8–33, Dec. 2023.
9. H. Xiong, S. Wang, Y. Zhu, Z. Zhao, Y. Liu, L. Huang, Q. Wang, and D. Shen, "DoctorGLM: Fine-tuning your chinese doctor is not a herculean task," Apr. 2023.
10. Y. B. Sree, A. Sathvik, D. S. Hema Akshith, O. Kumar, and B. S. Pranav Rao, "Retrieval-augmented generation based large language model chatbot for improving diagnosis for

- physical and mental health,” in 2024 6th International Conference on Electrical, Control and Instrumentation Engineering (ICECIE), pp. 1–8, IEEE, Nov. 2024.
11. S. Kirubakaran, J. W. Kathrine, G. M. Kanaga, M. Raja, R. G. Singh A, and Yuvarajan, “A RAG-based medical assistant especially for infectious diseases,” in 2024 International Conference on Inventive Computation Technologies (ICICT), IEEE, Apr. 2024.
 12. H. Yu, P. Guo, and A. Sano, “Zero-shot ECG diagnosis with large language models and retrieval-augmented generation,” pp. 650–663, 2023.
 13. M. Cremaschi, D. Ditolve, C. Curcio, A. Panzeri, A. Spoto, and A. Maurino, “Decoding the mind: A RAG-LLM on ICD-11 for decision support in psychology,” *Expert Syst. Appl.*, vol. 279, p. 127191, June 2025.
 14. H. Q. Yu and S. McGuinness, “An experimental study of integrating fine-tuned large language models and prompts for enhancing mental health support chatbot system,” *J. Med. Artif. Intell.*, June 2024.
 15. Z. Yang, E. Khatibi, N. Nagesh, M. Abbasian, I. Azimi, R. Jain, and A. M. Rahmani, “ChatDiet: Empowering personalized nutrition-oriented food recommender chatbots through an LLM-augmented framework,” *Smart Health*, vol. 32, p. 100465, June 2024.
 16. G. Dibenedetto, M. Polignano, P. Lops, and G. Semeraro, “Prompting large language models for tailored exercise recommendations in office spaces,” pp. 77–88, 2024.
 17. C. Zakka, A. Chaurasia, R. Shad, A. R. Dalal, J. L. Kim, M. Moor, K. Alexander, E. Ashley, J. Boyd, K. Boyd, K. Hirsch, C. Langlotz, J. Nelson, and W. Hiesinger, “Almanac: Retrieval-augmented language models for clinical medicine,” *Res. Sq.*, May 2023.
 18. J. Ruan, Q. Su, Z. Chen, J. Huang, and Y. Li, “CPRS: a clinical protocol recommendation system based on LLMs,” *Int. J. Med. Inform.*, vol. 195, p. 105746, Mar. 2025.
 19. H.-W. Hu, Y.-C. Lin, C.-H. Chia, E. Chuang, and Y. Cheng Ru, “Leveraging large language models for generating personalized care recommendations in dementia,” in 2024 IEEE International Workshop on Electromagnetics: Applications and Student Innovation Competition (iWEM), vol. 1, pp. 1–4, IEEE, July 2024.
 20. Y. Lai, A. Kankanhalli, and D. Ong, “Human-AI collaboration in healthcare: A review and research agenda,” in *Proceedings of the 54th Hawaii International Conference on System Sciences*, Hawaii International Conference on System Sciences, 2021.
 21. C. J. Cai, S. Winter, D. Steiner, L. Wilcox, and M. Terry, ““hello AI”: Uncovering the onboarding needs of medical practitioners for human-AI collaborative decision-making,” *Proc. ACM Hum. Comput. Interact.*, vol. 3, pp. 1–24, Nov. 2019.
 22. D. Wang, L. Wang, Z. Zhang, D. Wang, H. Zhu, Y. Gao, X. Fan, and F. Tian, ““brilliant AI doctor” in rural clinics: Challenges in AI-powered clinical decision support system deployment,” in *Proceedings of the 2021 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems*, (New York, NY, USA), ACM, May 2021.
 23. DeepSeek-AI, D. Guo, D. Yang, H. Zhang et al., “DeepSeek-R1: Incentivizing reasoning capability in LLMs via reinforcement learning,” *arXiv [cs.CL]*, Jan. 2025.
 24. P. Lovibond and S. Lovibond, “The structure of negative emotional states: comparison of the depression anxiety stress scales (DASS) with the beck depression and anxiety inventories,” *Behav. Res. Ther.*, vol. 33, pp. 335–343, Mar. 1995.
 25. P. Lialiou and I. Maglogiannis, “Students’ burnout symptoms detection using smartwatch wearable devices: A systematic literature review,” *AI Sensors*, vol. 1, no. 1, p. 2, May 2025.
 26. H. Kazi, B. S. Chowdhry, and Z. Memon, “MedChatBot: An UMLS based chatbot for medical students,” *Int. J. Comput. Appl.*, vol. 55, pp. 1–5, Oct. 2012.
 27. V. Katariya and V. S. Gutte, “Intelligent healthbot for transforming healthcare.”
 28. P. I. Prayitno, R. P. Pujio Leksono, F. Chai, R. Aldy, and W. Budiharto, “Health chatbot using natural language processing for disease prediction and treatment,” in 2021 1st International

- Conference on Computer Science and Artificial Intelligence (ICCSAI), vol. 1, pp. 62–67, IEEE, Oct. 2021.
29. A. Vaswani, N. Shazeer, N. Parmar, J. Uszkoreit, L. Jones, A. N. Gomez, N. Kaiser, and I. Polosukhin, “Attention is all you need,” *Adv. Neural Inf. Process. Syst.*, vol. 30, 2017.
 30. J. Devlin, M.-W. Chang, K. Lee, and K. Toutanova, “BERT: Pre-training of deep bidirectional transformers for language understanding,” *arXiv [cs.CL]*, Oct. 2018.
 31. OpenAI, J. Achiam, S. Adler, S. Agarwal, L. Ahmad, I. Akkaya, F. L. Aleman, D. Almeida, J. Altenschmidt, S. Altman, S. Anadkat, T. Avila, J. Zhuang, W. Zhuk, and B. Zoph, “GPT-4 technical report,” *arXiv [cs.CL]*, Mar. 2023.
 32. H. Touvron, L. Martin, K. Stone, P. Albert, A. Almahairi, Y. Babaei, N. Bashlykov, S. Batra, A. Bhargava, R. Stojnic, S. Edunov, and T. Scialom, “Llama 2: Open foundation and fine-tuned chat models,” *arXiv [cs.CL]*, July 2023.
 33. M. Argymbay, S. Khan, N. Ahmad, M. Salih, and Y. Mamatjan, “A smart recommender system for stroke risk assessment with an integrated strokebot,” *J. Med. Biol. Eng.*, Dec. 2024.
 34. A. Berger, D. Berghaus, A. H. Bashir, L. Grigull, L. Fendrich, T. A. Lagones, H. Högl, G. Ernst, R. Schmidt, D. Bascom, T. Deußner, T. Bell, M. Lübbering, and R. Sifa, “Advancing personalized medicine: A scalable LLM-based recommender system for patient matching,” in *2024 IEEE International Conference on Big Data (BigData)*, pp. 5876–5883, Dec. 2024.
 35. F. Farhat, “ChatGPT as a complementary mental health resource: A boon or a bane,” *Ann. Biomed. Eng.*, vol. 52, pp. 1111–1114, May 2024.
 36. T. Glm, A. Zeng, B. Xu, B. Wang, C. Zhang, D. Yin, D. Zhang, Z. Rojas, Z. Du, Z. Hou, and Z. Wang, “ChatGLM: A family of large language models from GLM-130B to GLM-4 all tools,” *arXiv [cs.CL]*, June 2024.
 37. P. Lewis, E. Perez, A. Piktus, F. Petroni, V. Karpukhin, N. Goyal, H. Küttler, M. Lewis, W.-T. Yih, T. Rocktäschel, S. Riedel, and D. Kiela, “Retrieval-augmented generation for knowledge-intensive NLP tasks,” *arXiv [cs.CL]*, May 2020.
 38. G. Xiong, Q. Jin, Z. Lu, and A. Zhang, “Benchmarking retrieval-augmented generation for medicine,” *Annu Meet Assoc Comput Linguistics*, vol. abs/2402.13178, Feb. 2024.
 39. A. Lozano, S. L. Fleming, C.-C. Chiang, and N. Shah, “Clinfo.ai: An open-source retrieval augmented large language model system for answering medical questions using scientific literature,” *Pac. Symp. Biocomput.*, vol. 29, pp. 8–23, 2024.
 40. A. Casey, *Stress Management, Approaches for Preventing and Reducing Stress*. MA, UK: Harvard Health Publications, 2013.
 41. H. Benson and M. Z. Klipper, *The Relaxation Response*. New York, NY: William Morrow Paperbacks, 2000.
 42. M. Greenberg, *The Stress Proof Brain*. Oakland, CA: New Harbinger Publications, 2017.
 43. J. Kabat-Zinn, *Full Catastrophe Living*. New York, NY: Random House, 2013.
 44. E. Selhub, *The stress management handbook: A practical guide to staying calm, keeping cool, and avoiding blow-ups*. New York, NY: Skyhorse Publishing, Jan. 2019.
 45. R. M. Sapolsky, *Why Zebras Don’t Get Ulcers, An Updated Guide To Stress, Stress Related Diseases, and Coping*. New York, NY: Barnes & Noble Books, 2000.
 46. U. R. Rout and J. K. Rout, *Stress Management for Primary Healthcare Professionals*. New York, NY: Springer, 2002.
 47. S. Es, J. James, L. Espinosa Anke, and S. Schockaert, “RAGAS: Automated Evaluation of Retrieval Augmented Generation,” in *Proceedings of the 18th Conference of the European Chapter of the Association for Computational Linguistics: System Demonstrations*, St. Julians, Malta, pp. 150–158, Mar. 2024.
 48. W. Webber, A. Moffat, and J. Zobel, “A similarity measure for indefinite rankings,” *ACM Trans. Inf. Syst.*, vol. 28, pp. 1–38, Nov. 2010.